

THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY AND PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS IN SHAPING CHILDREN'S HEALTH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11018596>

Abstract

The article discusses the role of the family and preschool institutions in shaping children's health

Key words

Physical development, physical perfection, sports, preschooler, modernization, factors, integration, physical qualities.

Modern development in Uzbekistan is associated with modernization in the field of Education, which primarily affects the problems of the formation of the younger generation, which is integrated into modern society. A person who is focused on a healthy lifestyle can be successful in different areas of life.

Many negative factors affect the health of children: an increasing deterioration in the environment, a decrease in the standard of living throughout the country, a decrease in the level of social guarantees for children in the areas of spiritual and physical development, a lack of time and funds for parents to fully meet the needs of children, an increase in the number of incomplete families,

In these conditions, the problem of preserving and strengthening the health of preschoolers becomes especially urgent. Today's children are the future of the state. Within the framework of the state concept of preserving children's health, much attention is paid to strengthening children's health, and, above all, to the formation of a healthy lifestyle for a child. The health-saving nature of education and upbringing is especially important in preschool educational institutions, where the child receives basic knowledge from many sciences, including about his body, at this stage the child understands and accepts the value of a healthy lifestyle.

Simultaneously with the use of innovative technologies, the most important factor in influencing a child's personality is the atmosphere of family emotional ties. Parental love provides children with emotional protection and psychological comfort, gives life support, and the love and boundless trust of the child make him especially susceptible to their effects. Special psychological,

pedagogical and sociological research (A.I. Zakharov, Y.P. Litvinene, A.N. Demidova, V.Ya. Titarenko, O.L. Zvereva, E.P. Arnautova) showed that the family urgently needs the help of specialists at all stages of preschool childhood. It is obvious that the family and kindergarten, having their own special functions, cannot replace each other and must interact in the name of the full development of a preschool child.

Today, recognizing the priority of family education over public education, assigning responsibility for the upbringing of children to parents, we understand that this requires a new relationship between the family and preschool. These relations are defined by the concepts of "cooperation" and "interaction".

Therefore, kindergarten should become an open educational system, i.e., on the one hand, make the pedagogical process more free, flexible, differentiated, humane on the part of the teaching staff, and on the other hand, involve parents in the educational process of a preschool institution.

The tasks and content of educating older preschool children are multifaceted. A special place among them is occupied by the problems of protecting children's health and their physical education, since the full development of a child depends on the effectiveness of solving these problems.

Older preschool children have all the prerequisites for the stable formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle:

- mental processes are actively developing, self-esteem and a sense of responsibility are growing;
- "positive changes in physical and functional development are noticeable; children are able to maintain and demonstrate correct posture;
- children are able to independently carry out household tasks, possess self-service skills, make strong-willed efforts to achieve their goals in the game, in the manifestation of physical activity."

The physiological state of older preschool children is greatly influenced by their psycho-emotional state, which, in turn, depends on mental attitudes. Therefore, scientists identify the following aspects of a healthy lifestyle of older preschoolers:

An analysis of all programs for the upbringing and development of older preschool children shows that physical education occupies a leading place in the educational process, in contrast to the formation of older preschoolers' ideas about a healthy lifestyle. Such attention of preschool children to the physical development of an older preschooler is due to the peculiarities of the children's

body: the child grows, his height increases, body weight increases, motor activity develops, etc.

To form the ideas of older preschoolers about a healthy lifestyle, special exercises are needed to strengthen the health of children, a system of physical education. To do this, morning exercises are held daily in the kindergarten group, the purpose of which is to create a cheerful, cheerful mood in children, strengthen their health, develop dexterity, physical strength. Morning gymnastics and special physical education classes in the gym are accompanied by music, which "favorably affects the emotional sphere of the older preschooler, promotes a good mood of children, forms their ideas about a healthy lifestyle."

Outdoor games are of great importance for the formation of older preschoolers' ideas about a healthy lifestyle. They are held in a group, in special classes, during walks and in the intermediate intervals between classes. Outdoor games are necessarily included in music classes. The games of older preschoolers are organized by the teacher, but most often by the children themselves. "As a rule, children play in small groups. The feeling of joy and independence in the game stimulates older preschoolers to strive for even more physical activity and to organize a healthy lifestyle."

For children to successfully learn the rules of a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary that all of them are strictly followed by adults, both in preschool and in the family. Therefore, an important condition for the formation of ideas about healthy lifestyle in older preschool children is continuity in the work of parents to solve this problem. During the experiment, the following work was carried out with the parents:

1. In the reception room of the senior group, a folding folder and a "Aibolit" corner are designed for parents, which contains information about the most important areas of healthy lifestyle (how to spend a weekend at home with benefits, why onions are useful, how to protect yourself from colds, etc.)

2. The Open Health Day introduced preschool parents to the wellness resources of the preschool; a photo exhibition "Be healthy" and the consultation "Drink herbal decoctions – be healthy" was organized jointly with parents.

The work on interaction with the family is based on unity, when the purpose and objectives of raising a child are well understood not only by the educator, but also by parents, when the family is familiar with the methods and techniques of physical education and wellness work in kindergarten, and teachers use the best experience of family education. It is very important to use

an individual approach in working with the family based on taking into account health, interests and needs.

During the survey, it was revealed that not all parents are involved in sports, the most effective forms of kindergarten work with parents are considered: joint sports holidays, open classes. From this, I concluded that parents are ready to cooperate with the kindergarten and participate in joint sports events. The survey at this stage showed the next level of education of parents in health issues.

High – 8%

The average is 40%

Low – 52%

Most parents consider health as the absence of diseases, without taking into account the interconnection of all components of health, and they see the means of improving the child's body in therapeutic measures.

Parents have common ideas about promoting children's health and health culture, but need to enrich their knowledge and practical recommendations.

Work with parents was carried out in parallel with work with children. Teachers have developed a long-term plan, which includes a variety of activities with the participation of parents of children and teachers aimed at uniting parent and child groups. All events were planned taking into account the integration of educational fields.

Joint work with the family was based on the principles of voluntariness, community, systematic and consistent work, as well as an individual approach to each family. Individual forms of interaction with parents were especially effective, who showed a low level of consciousness and competence in health issues during the testing process.

As a result of the work carried out, a system of relationships with the family was built. Its effectiveness can be traced to the increased level of competence of parents and preschoolers in matters of health culture. This ultimately had a positive effect on the development of motor activity and physical fitness of preschoolers.

According to the same methodology as at the beginning of the work, a survey of parents was conducted, the results showed a positive trend in changing the level of competence in matters of health culture. The high level of competence increased from 8% to 28% compared to the first survey, the average from 40% to 52%, and now only 5% of the parents surveyed have a low level.

Thus, the work I have studied and done confirms the importance and necessity of its implementation in a preschool institution. Having built a system of work based on an integrated approach in interaction with parents to form a culture of children's health, positive changes have been achieved:

- The indicators of preschool children have improved;
- The level of information competence has increased, motivational readiness for recreational activities in the family and a conscious attitude of parents and children to the issue of health care has been formed;
- Parents began to show interest, an active position and high responsibility for the ongoing wellness activities in the preschool;
- The nature of the parents' appeal to the teacher has changed in the direction of interest in the issues of children's health improvement;
- Family relationships have improved due to the understanding of one's own child, an adequate assessment of his health and physical development;

The health of older preschool children is socially conditioned and depends on such factors as the state of the environment, the health of parents and heredity, the living conditions and upbringing of a child in a family, in an educational institution. Significant factors in our study that form a positive attitude of children to a healthy lifestyle are the system of education and training, including physical education, mental health protection, as well as preventive measures aimed at health care in preschoolers.

The objectives of a healthy lifestyle of older preschoolers are to foster a culture of health and healthy lifestyle habits, the formation of a system of concepts aimed at the child's awareness of his "I", the capabilities of his body, the dependence of his health on actions, deeds, habits. These tasks are realized during classes, conversations, outdoor games, and research work based on calm, friendly relationships.

The forms of work with vary: quizzes, nature excursions are held, parents are involved in the work, much attention is paid to the individual interests of children. Therefore, the main task of health-saving pedagogy is such a regime of work and recreation for preschoolers, in which children maintain high efficiency throughout the entire period of classes.

As a result of the theoretical and experimental research, we clarified the content of the concept of "healthy lifestyle" in modern research.

A healthy lifestyle in our study is an active form of behavior of children, ensuring the preservation of mental and physical health, increasing the adaptive capabilities of the body, its maximum capacity. This includes a favorable

emotional climate in the family, friendly, benevolent attitude of parents to each other and the child; this is proper organized nutrition, the use of outdoor exercise and sufficient activity of the individual, and of course the correct exemplary behavior of adults, their negative attitude to bad habits. By the formation of a healthy lifestyle, we understand a specially organized pedagogical process that promotes the harmonization of personality from the standpoint of health conservation.

Analyzing modern approaches to the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle, we also tried to consider the essence of the interaction between the family and the preschool in the formation of a healthy lifestyle, which consists in providing the child with an individual style of healthy behavior through the creation and implementation of pedagogical conditions as a set of prerequisites organizing pedagogical activities in a preschool institution.

Considering the state of theory and practice on the problem under study, positive experience was gained in organizing the process of hygienic education of older preschoolers. The ratio of theoretical analysis materials and conclusions obtained as a result of studying positive experience in organizing the process of forming a healthy lifestyle in older groups allowed us to develop a program of experimental work.

In the course of the experimental work, the ascertaining forming and control experiments were carried out.

Comparing the results of the control experiment with the results of the ascertaining experiment, we can note a tendency to increase valeological knowledge in older preschoolers. The model of interrelation of elements of the lifestyle of older preschoolers reflects the interaction of various components of the environment: labor, educational, household, as well as personal components: peers, educators and parents.

Revealing the content of the components of healthy lifestyle, it should be noted that all spheres of life of children of this age - labor, social, family, leisure - are interconnected through communication with peers, educators, parents, those whom we called subjects of education. This model, in our opinion, reflects the socio-pedagogical side of the process of formation of healthy lifestyle of older preschoolers. Thus, our research has shown that the formation of the foundations of a healthy lifestyle is possible through a special organized interaction between the family and the DOW.

The effectiveness of interaction between the family and preschool institutions in the formation of a healthy lifestyle for older preschool children is

ensured by the joint activities of teachers, parents and children aimed at preserving and strengthening children's health.

Full-fledged health and harmonious physical development of the child is what all parents strive for. Unfortunately, in recent years, we have all been struck by the sad statistics on the incidence of diseases in preschool children. One in three has physical disabilities. Of course, there are many reasons for this: environmental, social, genetic, and medical. One of them is the inattention of adults to the health of children. All of you, dear parents, love your children, treat them diligently when they get sick, but in everyday life you do not always use methods and means to prevent diseases and promote children's health.

Being a parent is harder today than ever before. If before the influence of parents on the child was exceptional, today television, movies, radio, comics or picture books often completely replace parents and bring results that are not always easy to foresee or correct. Besides, parents have less and less time to devote to their children.

The problem of fostering a culture of health among all participants in the educational process in kindergarten is especially relevant at the present stage of development of society. Modern living conditions place increased demands on human health, especially for preschool children. It is no secret that favorable conditions for the development, education and upbringing of a preschool child can be realized only if two social institutions – kindergarten and family - work closely together.

The modern activity of teachers of preschool educational institutions and parents to preserve and strengthen the health of the child, the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the basics of hygienic and physical culture has not only pedagogical, but also deep social significance. After all, children's health is the future of the country, the basis of its national security. Preserving and strengthening the health of preschoolers involves increasing the role of parents in improving children's health, introducing them to a healthy lifestyle, and creating traditions of family physical education. An important place in solving these socially significant tasks is occupied by a kindergarten, which acts as a kind of center for promoting a healthy lifestyle, fostering family culture, and forming parents' knowledge, skills and abilities on various aspects of preserving and strengthening the health of both children and adults. Only if the continuity of physical education and wellness work in kindergarten and family is realized, and joint purposeful activities of parents and teachers can a positive dynamics of

indicators characterizing the health of children and their orientation towards a healthy lifestyle be ensured.

At an early age, a child is not yet able to consciously and adequately follow basic hygiene and sanitation standards, take care of his own health and the health of others. All this requires parents to form a lifestyle that helps preserve their health.

The problem of preserving and strengthening children's health during the period of adaptation to kindergarten is especially relevant, since the admission of a child to kindergarten is often associated with severe experiences accompanied by a decrease in his activity (speech, play, motor). Parents should become an emotional support for the child. It is necessary to give the opportunity to gradually get used to new conditions, to provide kindergarten with complete information about the child's health. To ensure the normal physical development of children, it is necessary first of all to observe a hygienic regime, i.e. rational allocation of time for sleep, food, various activities and rest during the day, in accordance with the age characteristics of children. It is necessary that in the family, as well as in a preschool institution, the main requirement of the regime is fulfilled — accuracy in time and the correct alternation of regime processes, the change of some types of activities by others. Preschool plays an important role in a child's development. Here he receives primary education, acquires the ability to interact with other children and adults, and organize his own activities.

To solve this problem, a motor regime has been introduced in our kindergarten, which is provided by the integrated use of all forms of motor activity: morning gymnastics; physical education; outdoor and sports games; individual work; independent motor activity of children on a walk and in free play activities.

Healthy lifestyle habits instilled in children in kindergarten can be combined into a minimum program that the child must perform independently: It is quite obvious that a positive result can be achieved only with the close cooperation of the preschool institution and the family. Since the needs for a healthy lifestyle will be formed only with an unambiguous attitude towards them from parents and teachers. Only if this condition is met, the child will perceive a careful attitude to his health as an immutable truth, the only correct lifestyle. Be healthy and raise healthy children!

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